

MODELLING OF CREEP DEFORMATION

IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Summary

Metal-matrix composites of potential commercial interest are reinforced by fibres with much greater melting temperatures than the matrices. In likely service conditions the fibres will deform elastically. A model of high temperature composite deformation produced by elastic deformation of infinite fibres in a creeping matrix predicts a progressively decreasing creep rate that asymptotically approaches zero as the strain approaches an equilibrium value. A steady state creep rate can be established due to end effects and matrix shear in short-fibre and misaligned composites and in these cases the initial creep transient asymptotically approaches this steady state. The matrix can be indirectly strengthened and its creep behaviour significantly modified by the reinforcing phase in two different ways: (a) by the introduction of a threshold to matrix deformation and (b) by changing the deformation rates by suppressing glide in the matrix and requiring a climb-dominated deformation mechanism.

Introduction

Recent developments in the processing of metal-matrix composites that have produced more reliable structures and improved performance have led to renewed interest in modelling and prediction of the mechanical behaviour of these materials. Aluminium alloy matrices reinforced by refractory fibres, such as silicon carbide or alumina, have been particularly extensively investigated (1-3); however, few data have been released that indicate the extent of improvement in time dependent deformation and fracture of these composites relative to the creep performance of the matrix alloys. This paper will review the available models of creep in composite materials that are relevant to such aluminium-matrix systems. It will attempt to predict the ultimate level of creep performance that should be consistent with various fibre characteristics (such as aspect ratio and alignment) and will compare these predictions with available data.

Many of the models of creep in composites have been developed to describe the high temperature deformation that results when both matrix and reinforcement creep (4,5). This may be appropriate to many in-situ composites or to nickel-base matrices reinforced by refractory metal wires where the difference in melting temperature of the two phases can be relatively small. However, in aluminium-silicon carbide and aluminium-alumina composites the matrix and reinforcement operate at widely different homologous temperatures (0.4-0.7 and 0.1-0.3 respectively). Figure 1 shows deformation mechanism maps for Al (6), SiC (7) and Al₂O₃ (6); at the projected service stresses and temperatures of aluminium-matrix composites (20-100 MPa, 450-700 K) the matrix will be subject to creep rates that are many orders of magnitude greater than those of the fibres (even if all of the stress is considered to be carried by the fibres). Consequently, this paper will only consider the consequences of elastic deformation of the reinforcing phase in a creeping matrix. In a recent general review of creep deformation of metal-matrix composites McLean (8) has distinguished between direct composite strengthening, due to rule of mixtures effects, and indirect strengthening where the matrix behaviour is modified by the reinforcement; both effects will be considered in the following discussion.

Continuous aligned fibres

McLean (9) has modelled the time dependent deformation of continuous composites in which the fibres deform elastically at a rate determined by a creeping matrix. The fraction of the applied load carried by the fibres increases linearly with strain, in accord with Hooke's law. This is accompanied by off-loading and therefore decreasing the stress on the matrix which results in a steadily decreasing deformation rate of both matrix and fibre $\dot{\epsilon}$ (which must be identical to maintain material continuity). Various descriptions of creep deformation of metals have been proposed but in the following analysis it is assumed that the rate of creep of the matrix, $\dot{\epsilon}_m$, can be represented by the power-law expression,

$$\dot{\epsilon}_m = A \sigma^n \exp(-Q/RT) \quad (1)$$

σ is the applied stress, R is the gas constant and T is the temperature in K. A, n and Q are constants; for simple metals $n \sim 4$ and $Q \sim$ the activation energy for self diffusion. However, here we allow n and Q to have any values.

Figure 1 Deformation mechanism maps for (a) aluminium, (b) silicon carbide and (c) alumina showing the range of stresses and temperatures likely to be applied to aluminium-matrix composites.

Then the following expressions describe the creep rate as a function of strain and the strain as a function of time for the composite.

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \alpha \dot{\epsilon}_m \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_c} \right)^n \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_c - (\epsilon_c - \epsilon_0) \left[1 + \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon_0}{\epsilon_c} \right)^{n-1} \frac{(n-1)\alpha \dot{\epsilon}_m t}{\epsilon_c} \right]^{-\frac{1}{(n-1)}} \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha = \left(\frac{E_m V_m}{E_m V_m + E_f V_f} \right) V_m^{-n}$, $\epsilon_0 = \frac{\sigma}{E_m V_m + E_f V_f}$, $\epsilon_c = \frac{\sigma}{E_f V_f}$

E_m , E_f are Young's moduli and V_m , V_f volume fractions of matrix and fibres respectively. $\dot{\epsilon}_m$ is the creep rate of the matrix if it were carrying the full applied stress σ .

Equations 2 and 3 give neither a steady state nor a tertiary creep regime. Rather, there is a gradually decreasing strain rate as the equilibrium strain ϵ_0 is approached asymptotically. Consequently, the equations that have been developed to describe creep in simpler materials (10), where steady state deformation can occur, are quite inappropriate for such composites. Figure 2 shows the calculated variation in the strain rate at 1% strain plotted as a logarithmic function of applied stress for parameters appropriate to the $\gamma - \gamma'$ Cr₃C₂ in-situ composite at 825 °C; experimental data are included for comparison. At high stresses the curve is linear but its slope increases with decreasing stress as $\sigma_c = 0.01 E_f V_f$ is approached. Representation of creep deformation in such a material by a power law equation, which describes creep in the matrix well, would require that the apparent stress exponent n_{app} and activation energy Q_{app} should vary as indicated and that they should have magnitudes that are much greater than those associated with the matrix.

Although the early stages of creep in composites with continuous fibres follow the general behaviour described above, they also exhibit tertiary creep which can be associated with either the development of damage, such as fibre fragmentation, which transforms the material into a discontinuous composite, or a change in the matrix creep characteristics by microstructural or substructural instabilities that can affect the yield strength or the rate of deformation. Both aspects will be discussed in the following sections of this paper. However, for continuous composites with elastic fibres there is, in general, no steady state until the microstructure degrades; moreover, all the strain is fully recoverable, the strain energy being stored in the elastic fibres. Periods of constant creep rate are observed in metal matrix composites reinforced by short and/or misaligned fibres. The modification of the creep behaviour of elastic fibre/creeping matrix composites due to end effects at short fibres and to non-axial reinforcement will be considered below. Both factors lead to components of permanent (ie non-recoverable) strain.

Figure 2 (a) Variation in strain rate at 1% strain as a function of stress calculated from Equation 2 using parameters relevant to the $\gamma - \gamma' - \text{Cr}_3\text{C}_2$ eutectic at 1098 K. Experimental data are shown for reference. (b) n_{app} and Q_{app} for power law representation.

Discontinuous aligned fibres

When the fibres are of finite length the full stress is only carried by their central zones due to matrix shear in the vicinity of the fibre ends. The creep strength, relative to that of the continuous composite, is reduced due to two effects, viz (i) a reduction in the effective volume fraction of stress carrying fibre and (ii) matrix flow around the fibre ends that can accommodate differential straining of the phases. The latter factor leads to a constant strain rate $\Delta \dot{\epsilon}$ that is additional to the volume fraction normalised component that behaves as a continuous composite. Kelly and Street (11) have shown that for short rigid fibres, of aspect ratio l/d , in a matrix that deforms by power law creep.

$$\Delta \dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}_m \left[\phi \left(\frac{l}{d} \right)^{1 + \frac{1}{n}} V_f + V_m \right]^{-n} \quad (4)$$

where ϕ = load transfer parameter

$$= (0.667)^{\frac{1}{n}} \left[\frac{n}{2n+1} \right] \left[0.95 V_f^{-1/2} - 1 \right] \quad (5)$$

To a first approximation the combined effects can be written

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \alpha \dot{\epsilon}_m \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_c} \right)^n + \beta \dot{\epsilon}_m \quad (6)$$

where the constants α, β are functions of both fibre volume fraction and aspect ratio. Whereas for infinitely long fibres there is no steady state creep rate (ie $\beta = 0$), for short fibres a constant creep rate $\beta \dot{\epsilon}_m$ is approached at $\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_c$. The magnitude of $\beta \dot{\epsilon}_m$ is sensitive to the fibre aspect ratio and to the matrix stress exponent.

Figure 3 Theoretical creep curve obtained from Equations 4-6 by integration and using values of parameters relevant to (a) $\gamma - \gamma' - Cr_3C_2$ in-situ composite (100 MPa, 1273 K) and (b) 6061 Al-20 Vol% SiC (27.4 MPa, 561 K).

The time constant describing the approach to a steady creep rate is very sensitive to the stress exponent for matrix creep. Figures 3a and b show calculations for two composite systems for which experimental data are available and where the relevant parameters of the theory are known. Calculated creep curves for the $\gamma - \gamma' - Cr_3C_2$ in-situ composite at 1273 K/100 MPa, for which $n = 6$, show that the ideal continuous composite behaviour is approached for fibre aspect ratios ≥ 10 . In practice the aspect ratios associated with in-situ composites are much greater than this; however, it indicates that the creep behaviour should not be sensitive to fibre damage that might occur, for example, during cold loading. Nieh (2)

reports a value of $n = 3$ for matrix creep in composites of 20% SiC in 6061 Al; Figure 3b shows the calculated creep curves for this material at 561 K with a stress of 27.4 MPa. In this case the creep strength falls off rapidly with decreasing aspect ratio for $l/d \leq 100$. The sensitivity of the steady state creep rate, predicted from Equations 4 and 5, is shown graphically in Figure 4 which plots $\Delta\dot{\epsilon} / \dot{\epsilon}_m$ as a function of n for several values of fibre aspect ratio and $V_f = 0.2$.^m Clearly, in order to achieve an arbitrary reduction in creep rate, relative to the matrix behaviour, the composite must have fibres of much greater aspect ratio for low than for high values of n . A plot of the creep rate at 1% strain as a function of fibre aspect ratio is shown in Figure 5. Since such SiC whisker reinforced composites have $l/d \sim 10$ there would appear to be considerable scope for enhancing the creep strength by producing longer fibres. However, this model assumes that the matrix creep behaviour in the composite is similar to that in the absence of fibres. Further discussion below will indicate that indirect strengthening can significantly modify the matrix behaviour and, in particular, alter the effectiveness of short fibres in imparting creep strength. However, the general conclusion can be drawn that short fibres are most effective in matrices with high stress sensitivities for creep (ie high n).

Figure 4 Variation of $\Delta\dot{\epsilon} / \dot{\epsilon}_m$ as a function of matrix stress exponent n for various values of fibre aspect ratio l/d and $V_f = 0.2$ calculated from Equations 4 and 5.

Figure 5 Calculated variation in creep rate at 1% strain for the 6061 Al-20%SiC composite as a function of fibre aspect ratio at 616 K, 52 MPa.

Continuous misaligned fibres

The basis of strengthening of composites with aligned fibres is the off-loading of stress from the matrix to the reinforcing phase that is

required to constrain the matrix and reinforcement to maintain the same strain parallel to the fibres. When substantial components of stress do not coincide with the fibre axis it is possible to produce significant macroscopic strain by deformation of the matrix alone.

A tensile stress σ applied at an arbitrary angle θ to the direction of fibre alignment can be resolved into three components;

- (a) $\sigma_{zz} = \sigma \cos^2 \theta$ = a tensile stress parallel to the fibres
- (b) $\sigma_{xx} = \sigma \sin^2 \theta$ = a tensile stress normal to the fibres
- (c) $\sigma_{xz} = \sigma \sin \theta \cos \theta$ = a shear stress parallel to the fibres

Component (a) leads to deformation parallel to fibres which should be described by the models outlined above for continuous and for discontinuous composites. Components (b) and (c) can lead to composite deformation by matrix flow alone. Following the approach of Miles and McLean (12) in summing the strain rates produced by the three stress components acting independently (ie assuming no interactions), but modifying the treatment to allow for elastic fibre deformation the following expression is obtained for creep rate as a function of the misalignment of stress and fibre axis.

$$\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_m}{\dot{\epsilon}_c} = \left[\alpha \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_c} \right)^n + \beta \right] \left(\cos^{\alpha(n+1)} \theta - \frac{1}{2} \cos^{2n} \theta \sin^2 \theta \right) + f_1 (\sin \theta \cos \theta)^{n+1} + f_2 \sin^{2(n+1)} \theta \quad (7)$$

where $f_1 = \frac{3^{(n+1)/2}}{2}$ and $f_2 \sim 0.25$.

In the following discussion the aligned composite creep behaviour has been approximated by a power-law with a high stress exponent n_f to allow comparison with available experimental data

$$\text{ie } \alpha \dot{\epsilon}_m \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_c} \right)^n + \beta \dot{\epsilon}_m \equiv A \sigma^{n_f} \quad \text{where } n_f \gg n$$

For the (Co,Cr) - (Co,Cr)₇C₃ in-situ composite, where the stress exponent for creep of both matrix and composite are ~ 6.5 , this simple model adequately described the variation in creep rate with inclination of an applied tensile stress of 200 MPa at 825 °C, as shown in Figure 6. The same data have been used to compute the variation in stress to give various constant creep rates for this system as shown in Figure 7a. Both plots show that deviations of up to about 10 degrees between stress and fibre axis should be tolerated without adversely affecting the creep strength.

Similar calculations for the 6061 Al - 20%SiC alloy where stress exponents of 20.5 and 3 are reported for composite and matrix creep respectively are shown in Figure 7b. The level of anisotropy is predicted to

Figure 6 Minimum creep rate of $(\text{Co,Cr})\text{-Cr}_7\text{C}_3$ tested at 825°C with a stress of 200 MPa applied at various angles θ to the fibre axes. The curve is a plot of Equation 7.

Figure 7 Plots of the stress calculated using Equation 7 to cause the same strain rates in composites stressed at various directions to the fibre axes (a) $(\text{CoCr})\text{-Cr}_7\text{C}_3$ in-situ composites at 1098 K .

(b) 6061 Al-20\%SiC at 561 K .

decrease with increasing strain rate; similarly increasing deviations from axial stressing appears to be possible with increasing stress. However, these calculations also assume that the matrix performance is unaffected by the presence of the fibres, and this may give rise to significant errors.

Composites with randomly oriented fibres, such as the aluminium-Saffil system (13), are currently being investigated and it would be of interest to estimate the creep performance of these materials. If we approximate the composite with randomly oriented fibres to a structure composed of layers of aligned fibre composite with the layers randomly misoriented, an estimate of the creep behaviour can be obtained by treating the system as a super-composite. When a stress is applied it will be distributed between the layers so that the entire cross-section will deform at the same rate. If the stress to give a constant strain rate is known as a function of stress orientation $\sigma(\theta)$ (Figure 7) then the average stress carried by the randomly oriented composite can be obtained by integration:

$$\sigma_{av} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi/2} \alpha(\theta) d\theta \quad (8)$$

Figure 8 compares the calculated behaviour of 6061 Al-20%SiC with randomly oriented fibres with the experimental data for the matrix and aligned fibre composite. This clearly predicts a potential for matrix strengthening with un-aligned fibres.

Figure 8 Comparison of calculated creep rates as a function of stress for randomly oriented 6061 Al-20%SiC with experimental data for the 6061 Al matrix and the aligned 6061 Al-20% SiC composite at 561 K

Indirect matrix strengthening

In all of the previous discussion the matrix creep rate $\dot{\epsilon}_m$ has been an

important parameter in determining the creep behaviour of the composites. In particular, the steady state creep components resulting from end effects at discontinuous fibres and misalignment of the reinforcement are both predicted to scale with $\dot{\epsilon}_m$. However there is clear experimental evidence that both the stress exponent n and activation energy associated with creep of composites tend to be significantly larger than the values associated with the unreinforced matrices (2,5). Also the models based on rule of mixtures stress distributions do not predict differences in mechanical behaviour associated with the scale of the microstructure; however, very large increases in creep strength have been reported to result from microstructural refinement. Both factors point to a significant modification of the matrix behaviour due to the presence of the fibres. Indeed the properties of particle strengthened alloys are dominated by such effects suggesting that the shape of the dispersed phase is relatively unimportant.

Attempts have been made to rationalise these differences by expressing the power-law creep equation in terms of an effective, rather than applied, stress (14);

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A' (\sigma - \sigma_0)^{n'} \exp(-Q'/RT) \quad (9)$$

The dispersed phase can influence the creep rate in two quite different manners.

(a) The threshold-, or friction-, stress σ_0 associated with the particles can present a resistance to deformation. By attributing suitable values of σ_0 to a composite it is certainly possible to obtain values of n' and Q' that are consistent with those associated with the matrix. However, it is difficult to measure σ_0 independently and most analyses have been based on manipulation of creep data (14).

The threshold stress σ_0 in fibre reinforced alloys is most likely to be the stress required to cause Orowan bowing between the fibres (15).

$$\sigma_0 = \alpha \frac{\mu b}{r} \quad (10)$$

where r is the fibre radius, μ is the shear modulus and b is the Burgers vector of the matrix and α is a constant (<1) that depends on volume fraction. This certainly introduces a type of strengthening that increases with decreasing fibre size as is observed. However, taking values of the parameters relevant to Al-SiC composites ($\mu = 2.54 \times 10^4$ MPa, $b = 2.60 \times 10^{-4}$ μm and $r \sim 1$ μm) this would predict $\sigma_0 < 6.5$ MPa which gives a much smaller level of strengthening than is observed.

This type of mechanical strengthening will be more important if sub-micron reinforcement can be established. For example, $\sigma_0 \sim 60$ MPa for $r = 0.1$ μm . However, finely dispersed phases are microstructurally unstable at high temperatures, being subject to both spheroidization (if fibres) and coarsening (for both fibres and particulates) (16). Consequently, when the creep strength of a composite depends critically on the morphology of the reinforcing phase, there should be a progressive increase in creep rate for

a given stress due to diffusional degradation of the microstructure. For example, particle or fibre coarsening is well represented by the Lifshitz-Slyozov-Wagner kinetic equation

$$r^3 = r_0^3 + Kt \quad (11)$$

where r , r_0 are the final and initial particle radii, K is a temperature dependent kinetic constant and t is time. Dyson and McLean (17) show that combining Equations 9, 10 and 11 gives the following expression for creep rate as a function of time,

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \left[\sigma - \frac{\alpha \mu b}{r_0 \left(1 + \frac{Kt}{r_0^3} \right)^{1/3}} \right]^n \quad (12)$$

This qualitatively predicts the dominant tertiary creep regime that is characteristic of many engineering alloys which depend on particle strengthening. However, Dyson and McLean have shown that quantitative analysis of the long term creep behaviour of some nickel-base superalloys cannot be reconciled by this model.

In the case of fibre reinforced materials, spheroidization to progressively reduce the aspect ratio of the fibres is also likely to have a profound effect on the creep behaviour by altering the level of direct strengthening discussed above. Nichols (18) shows that there is a characteristic time τ associated with the detachment of spheres of diameter d from the ends of a fibre

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= \frac{8K'}{d^3} \quad \text{for volume diffusion} \\ &= \frac{16K''}{d^4} \quad \text{for interface diffusion} \end{aligned}$$

This will lead to a time dependent fibre aspect ratio

$$(l/d) = (l/d)_{\text{original}} - 2t/\tau$$

Since the creep rate is predicted to be very sensitive to l/d this could be a major effect.

(b) The presence of particles can also influence the rate of deformation by requiring a change in the mechanism of creep. In single phase alloys steady state deformation can be established when there is a balance between dislocation recovery and hardening; most of the strain is thought to accumulate during the rapid hardening stage which occurs by dislocation glide while the time dependence is due to diffusion controlled climb that leads to recovery of the dislocation substructure. If particles or fibres

present barriers to glide in the matrix and require all dislocation motion to occur by climb, then the deformation rate can be reduced by a factor $\geq 10^{-4}$ without influencing the stress at which flow can occur (19).

Dyson and McLean (17) showed that while the trends in the shapes of creep curves in several nickel-base superalloys were incompatible with there being time dependent changes in a strength controlling friction stress, there was a strong empirical correlation between $\dot{\epsilon}$ and elapsed creep strain. Henderson and McLean (20) have confirmed by analysis of creep strain transients following stress drop experiments, that the changes in σ_0 associated with these alloys are too small to account for the observed strain-rate acceleration; however, the kinetics of recovery increase significantly with accumulated strain. The causes of this strain-controlled softening have not been unambiguously identified although it is thought to be associated with evolution of the dislocation substructure, either by the development of a mis-match dislocation network at the particle matrix interfaces which may alter the dislocation climb kinetics or by the generation of a progressively increasing density of mobile dislocations.

General discussion and conclusions

In view of the large difference in melting temperatures of the constituent phases of many proposed metal matrix composites it is unlikely that both phases will deform by the same mechanism. The most likely combination will be of elastically deforming fibres in a creeping matrix. The direct strengthening from rule of mixtures stress partitioning is greatest for infinitely-long, well aligned fibres but the creep performance is significantly degraded by reduction in fibre aspect ratio and in deviations in alignment. The matrix creep behaviour can be modified significantly by the presence of the fibres and this complicates the interpretation of the simple rule-of-mixtures models.

One particularly important factor is the sensitivity of the creep strength to fibre aspect ratio which is controlled by the stress exponent, n , for matrix creep. The simple single phase matrix alloys, in the absence of reinforcement, are generally characterised by relatively small stress exponents which lead to a rapid fall off in creep strength with quite large aspect ratios (≤ 100 for $n = 3$). However, when fibres are added the value of n for creep is often very large (up to ~ 20) and this allows much shorter fibres to be effective.

The principal conclusions from this analysis are listed below.

- 1 There is no steady state creep rate for well-aligned fibres of infinite length deforming elastically in a creeping matrix; the creep rates progressively fall to asymptotically approach zero as the strain approaches an equilibrium value.
- 2 A steady state component of creep rate is produced in short fibre composites due to matrix flow around fibre ends.
- 3 Off-axis loading of fibre composites can also lead to steady state creep due to the non-axial components of stress. This causes degradation in creep performance with misalignment.

- 4 Indirect matrix strengthening can result from either mechanical effects due to the introduction of thresholds for matrix deformation or by suppression of the glide component of creep deformation in the matrix and its replacement by full dislocation-climb creep.

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